

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 61(2) (2025) 312-319

EISSN 2543-5426

Phytochemical contents and antioxidant potentials of *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench (Sorghum), *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. (Roselle) and their varying blends

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ABSTRACT

The use of natural ingredients in food products has gained wide acceptance because of their health benefits for both humans. *Sorghum bicolor* and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* possess abundant phytochemicals and bioactive compounds that promote health and wellness. This research was carried out to examine the phytochemical content and antioxidant activities of *Sorghum bicolor*, *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., and their blends. The leaf sheaths of *Sorghum bicolor* and calyces of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* were procured, dried till constant weight, then pulverised to assess their phytochemical compositions qualitatively and quantitatively. In addition to undiluted sorghum and roselle, blends comprising 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle, 25% Sorghum + 75% Roselle, and 50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle were derived, to make a total of five treatments for evaluation. The DPPH activities of the plants and their blends were also assessed. The results showed that saponin, alkaloids, flavonoid, tannin and reducing sugar were found in the blends. There were significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in phytochemical composition of *Sorghum bicolor*, Roselle and their different blends. Tannin and Saponin contents were significantly ($p < 0.05$) highest (125.67, 65.19, respectively) in 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle and lowest in 100% Roselle (85.42) and 100% Roselle (52.19). Alkaloid and reducing sugar followed the same trend with 100% Roselle having significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher values (59.12, 12.89), while 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle had the lowest value of 40.76, and 7.82 respectively. Flavonoid was significantly ($p < 0.05$) the highest (82.31) in 50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle and lowest in 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle. The antioxidant activity measured via DPPH was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) across treatments with 50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle recording the highest (66.53), 100% Sorghum had the lowest (49.69), while 100% Roselle, 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle and 50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle had values of 65.20, 64.13 and 57.20 respectively. The combination of *Sorghum bicolor* and roselle blends presents greater antioxidative

properties, with great potentials for the reducing lipid oxidation and microbial activities that can lead to food spoilage, thus improving the shelf life of food and ensuring the safe consumption of such food products in which they are embedded.

Keywords: phytochemical, antioxidant, sorghum, roselle, blends, *Sorghum bicolor*, *Hibiscus sabdariffa*

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent times, there has been a growing interest in incorporating natural ingredients which has various health benefits into food formulations, with the aim of enhancing the nutritional value of food and the overall well-being of humans. *Sorghum bicolor*, a cereal grain, and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., (Roselle) a tropical flowering plant, are both rich in phytochemical profiles and significant antioxidant activity (Awika and Rooney, 2005).

Sorghum bicolor is known for its abundance of phytochemicals, including polyphenols, flavonoids, tannins, and anthocyanins (Dykes and Rooney 2006).

These bioactive compounds exhibit various health-promoting properties, such as anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, and anti-diabetic effects. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. commonly is equally renowned for its phytochemical richness, particularly anthocyanins, flavonoids, and organic acids (Tsai *et al.*, 2006). The synergistic combination of the phytochemicals inherent in these plants is an index of health benefits.

Antioxidants are pivotal in combating oxidative stress, a factor linked to numerous chronic illnesses (Edo *et al.*, 2023) By combining the antioxidant properties of *Sorghum bicolor* and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., there is possibility of a strong defense against oxidative harm, which could further prolong the shelf life and nutritional integrity of food items.

The antioxidant capacity of blends containing *Sorghum bicolor* and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L, exhibit notable abilities to scavenge free radicals due to their rich polyphenolic content (Dykes and Rooney, 2007). This research was therefore designed to evaluate the phytochemical content and antioxidant activities of *Sorghum bicolor*, *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., and their varying blends (Banwo *et al.*, 2022).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study site

The study was carried out at the Animal Products and Processing Laboratory, Department of Animal Science, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

2. 2. Sourcing of Materials

The study utilised the leaf sheath of *Sorghum bicolor* (Figure 1) and Roselle (Figure 2), which were procured from Bodija market in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria. They were oven dried at 80 °C till reaching constant weight.

After this drying period, they were pulverised. The powdered materials were then packed into polythene bags and stored in air-tight containers at room temperature prior to blending and laboratory analysis.

Figure 1. *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench leaf sheath.

Figure 2. Dried Roselle calyces.

2. 3. Experimental design

Five different treatment combinations were derived from the pulverised materials thus; T1: 100% Sorghum, T2: 100% Roselle, T3: 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle, T4: 25% Sorghum + 75% Roselle, and T5: 50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle, and arranged in a completely randomised design.

2. 4. Qualitative Phytochemical Screening of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle

The initial qualitative assessment of the phytochemical content involved screening the extract to ascertain the presence of secondary metabolites, following the methodology outlined by Harborne (1998) and Parekh and Chanda (2007). Alkaloids were identified qualitatively using dragendroff reagent (potassium bismuth iodide), flavonoids were detected with Benedict's solutions (Adamu *et al.*, 1970), saponins were determined via a frothing test, tannins were assessed using wohler's test, and phenols were detected using ferric chloride solution, as detailed by Ajuru *et al.* (2017).

2. 5. Quantitative Phytochemical Screening of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle

Quantitative analysis of certain phytochemicals involved determining phytate levels according to AOAC (1990) protocols, saponins were quantified using the double solvent extraction gravimetric method outlined by Harborne (1973), phenols were quantified using the Folin Ciocalteu reagent method (McDonald *et al.*, 2001), alkaloids were quantified following the alkaline precipitation gravimetric method described by Harborne (1973), tannins were quantified using the Folin-Denis method (Polshettiwar *et al.*, 2007), and flavonoids were quantified using the procedure outlined by Harborne (1973).

2. 6. DPPH activities of *Sorghum* and Roselle and their blends

The radical scavenging activity was assessed using a spectrophotometric technique based on the reduction of a methanol solution containing 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), following the method described by Blois (1958). Briefly, one milliliter of varying concentrations of the extracts, including both essential oil and methanol extracts, dissolved in methanol, was mixed with an equal volume of a 0.2 mM methanol solution of DPPH. After vigorous shaking, the mixture was allowed to incubate at room temperature in the dark for 30 minutes.

Subsequently, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm against a blank using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan), with absolute methanol serving as the zero point for the instrument. The DPPH solution was freshly prepared each day, stored in a darkened flask covered with aluminium foil, and refrigerated at 4 °C until further use. The inhibition of free radicals, expressed as a percentage (I%), was determined using the formula:

$$I (\%) = (A_{\text{blank}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{blank}} \times 100$$

where A_{blank} represents the absorbance of the control reaction containing all reagents except the test compound, and A_{sample} denotes the absorbance of the test compound. The concentration of the extract required to achieve 50% inhibition (IC₅₀) was determined from a graph plotting inhibition percentage against extract concentration. A lower IC₅₀ value indicates higher antioxidant activity. All experiments were conducted in triplicate, with ascorbic acid employed as a positive control.

2. 7. Statistical analysis

The data generated from the study was subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between means was determined by Scheffe multiple comparison test using SPSS 16.0.1 for Windows.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the qualitative phytochemical composition of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle Blends. Saponin, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and reducing sugars were found in *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle Blends used in this study.

Table 1. Qualitative phytochemical of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle Blends.

Treatments	Tannin	Saponin	Alkaloid	Reducing sugar	Flavonoid
100% Sorghum	+++	++	++	+	+++
100% Roselle	+++	++	++	+	+++
75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle	++++	++	++	+	++
25% Sorghum + 75% Roselle	+++	++	++	+	++
50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle	+++	++	++	+	+++

Remarks key:

- (++++) Present in an abundant amount
- (+++) Present in an appreciable amount
- (++) Present in a moderate amount
- (+) Present in a traceable amount
- (-) completely absent

Table 2. Quantitative Phytochemical of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle Blends.

Treatments	Tannin (mg/100g)	Saponin (mg/100g)	Alkaloid (mg/100g)	Reducing sugar (mg/100g)	Flavonoid (mg/100g)
100% Sorghum	98.91±0.23	57.17±0.06 ^c	55.36±0.05 ^b	10.45±0.05 ^b	82.31±0.17 ^a
100% Roselle	85.42±0.13 ^e	54.63±0.17 ^d	59.12±0.01 ^a	12.89±0.09 ^a	79.69±0.02 ^b
75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle	125.67±0.52 ^a	65.19±0.02 ^a	40.76±0.06 ^c	7.82±0.1 ^e	62.46±0.05 ^e
25% Sorghum + 75% Roselle	106.53±0.65 ^b	61.49±0.05 ^b	46.49±0.14 ^d	8.54±0.05 ^d	66.53±0.08 ^d
50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle	93.75±0.62 ^d	52.91±0.03 ^e	48.53±0.12 ^c	9.65±0.04 ^c	76.75±0.05 ^c

^{a, b, c, d, e}: means with different superscripts on the same row are significantly different (p < 0.05)

Displayed on Table 2 is the quantitative phytochemical of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle blends. There were significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in phytochemical composition of *Sorghum bicolor*, Roselle and their different levels of combinations. Tannin and Saponin contents were significantly ($p < 0.05$) highest (125.67, 65.19, respectively) in 75% *Sorghum* + 25% Roselle and lowest in 100% Roselle (85.42) and 100% Roselle (52.19), respectively. Alkaloid and reducing sugar followed the same trend with 100% Roselle having significantly ($p < 0.05$) the highest (59.12, 12.89) while 75% *Sorghum* + 25% Roselle had the lowest (40.76, 7.82), respectively. Flavonoid was significantly ($p < 0.05$) the highest (82.31) in 50% *Sorghum* + 50% Roselle and lowest in 75% *Sorghum* + 25% Roselle.

DPPH Activities of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle, and their blends

Presented in Table 3 is the DPPH activities of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle, and their blends. The DPPH, which is a measure of antioxidant activity significantly ($p < 0.05$) varied throughout all the treatments with 50% *Sorghum* + 50% Roselle recording the highest (66.53) and 100% Roselle having the lowest (49.69).

Table 3. DPPH Activities of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle Blends.

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
DPPH	49.69 ^c	65.20 ^b	64.13 ^c	57.20 ^d	66.53 ^a
SEM	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03

a,b,c,d,e: means with different superscripts on the same row are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

T1: 100% *Sorghum*

T2: 100% Roselle

T3: 75% *Sorghum* + 25% Roselle

T4: 25% *Sorghum* + 75% Roselle

T5: 50% *Sorghum* + 50% Roselle

DPPH: 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl

SEM: Standard Error of Mean

Parameters

4. DISCUSSION

Phytochemicals are naturally occurring compounds in plants which significantly enhance meat preservation by providing antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, which slow down spoilage and extend shelf life. Studies show that incorporating plant extracts rich in phytochemicals into meat products can reduce lipid oxidation and microbial growth, thus maintaining quality and safety (Stoilova *et al.*, 2007). These effects are attributed to compounds like phenols and flavonoids, which effectively neutralize free radicals and inhibit pathogen proliferation (Yanishlieva *et al.*, 2006). The phytochemical composition of *Sorghum bicolor* and Roselle revealed significant differences in their individual profiles and various combinations. Tannins and saponins were highest in the 75% *Sorghum* + 25% Roselle blends

and lowest in 100% Roselle. This showed that Sorghum boosts tannin and saponin levels. However, alkaloids and reducing sugars were highest in 100% Roselle and lowest in the 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle blend, indicating Roselle contributes more to these phytochemicals. Flavonoids were highest in the 50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle blend and lowest in the 75% Sorghum + 25% Roselle blend. These differences are likely due to the unique chemical make-up of Sorghum and Roselle. Research has showed that Sorghum is rich in tannins and saponins, which have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits (Awika and Rooney, 2004). Roselle is known for its high alkaloid and reducing sugar content, offering health benefits like blood pressure reduction and cancer prevention (Tsai *et al.*, 2012). The different phytochemical levels in the combinations highlight the individual contributions of each plant, enhancing their nutritional and medicinal value. DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) is a stable free radical commonly used to evaluate the antioxidant activity of ingredients, reflecting their ability to neutralize free radicals. Higher DPPH values indicate stronger antioxidant properties, suggesting better potential for preserving ingredient quality and extending shelf life. The significant variation ($p < 0.05$) in DPPH values across treatments, with 50% Sorghum + 50% Roselle showing the highest (66.53) and 100% Roselle the lowest (49.69), may be due to the synergistic effects of combining different phytochemicals present in Sorghum and Roselle. This combination might enhance antioxidant activity more effectively than when either is used alone. Past studies, such as those by Moyo *et al.*, (2013) and Yang *et al.*, (2009), have demonstrated that mixed plant extracts can exhibit superior antioxidant properties compared to single extracts due to complementary interactions among their bioactive compounds.

5. CONCLUSION

The combination of *Sorghum bicolor* and roselle blends presents greater antioxidative properties which is potentially of great benefit to the reduction of lipid oxidation and microbial activities in food products.

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